

FORMA CIVITATIS

International Journal of Urban and
Territorial Morphological Studies

Vol. 2, N.1 , 2022

Cities in Evolution. Prix de Istanbul

Alessandro Camiz, Giorgio Verdiani, Martin Ebert editors

Grünberg Verlag
Weimar and Rostock, 2022

Cover image: Martin Ebert, The historical landscape of Erzi (Ingushetia, Russia), watercolor, 2022.

FORMA CIVITATIS International Journal of Urban and Territorial Morphological Studies

journal@formacivitatis.com
<http://www.formacivitatis.com/>

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Sponsors: Dynamic Research on Urban Morphology-DRUM laboratory, Istanbul

With the support of: Özyeğin University, Turkey, University of Florence, Italy, Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Norway

Cover design: Özge Özkuvancı

Layout and page design: Özge Özkuvancı, Eleonora Cecconi

Publisher: Grünberg Verlag,
Weimar and Rostock
<http://www.grunbergverlag.de/>

GRÜNBERGERLAG

Vol. 2, N. 1, 2022

ISSN 2748-2812 (Print); ISSN 2748-3134 (Online); ISBN: 9783933713681

Green open access
J123-2020-FC

RURAL UTOPIA AND WATER URBANISM. THE MODERN VILLAGE IN FRANCO'S SPAIN

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Lejeune, J.F. (2021) *Rural Utopia and Water Urbanism. The Modern Village in Franco's Spain* (DOM publishers: Berlin).

Jean-François Lejeune's book «The Modern Village in Franco's Spain» studies the reconstruction of the towns devastated in the civil war between 1936 and 1939. In the 1940s and 1950s Franco's government planted about 300 rural settlements in the Spanish countryside. The new settlements were embedded in the rural setting by the creation of man-made landscapes of dams, irrigation canals and electric power plants.

Lejeune's book analyses the ideological, political, and urbanistic principles in Franco's hydro-social programme of modernisation of the countryside. Under the backdrop of Franco's authoritarian dictatorship the villages, or pueblos, were designed as a 'rural utopia'. Each village is centred around a plaza mayor embodying the centre of urban life under the national-catholic ideology.

While describing the mind set of the Spanish architects, such as Alejandro de la Sota and José Luis Fernández del Amo, the book manages to link the movement for urban modernisation in Spain to the early-modernist movement romanticising the rural lifestyle in Germany and other European countries. He traces the search for an alternative modernity beyond the Mies- and Bauhaus- modernity. Lejeune's introduction manages to free the romantic modernist movement from its dark roots of ethnic and reactionary thinking and set them in the larger context of a more diverse approach to modernity in the beginning of the 20th century, such as Bruno Taut, Paul Schmitthenner and Richard Kauffmann.

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FORMA CIVITATIS: International journal of urban and territorial morphological studies (IJUTMS), Vol. 2, N. 1, 2022

The book shows also the reality of rural modernisation in Franco's Spain, where the motives of the alternative modern architecture necessarily got tainted by the autocratic and nationalist agenda of the regime. The *pueblos de colonización* shown by Lejeune show traits very familiar to works such as Schulte-Frohlinde's plans for German settlements in the east (Schulte-Frohlinde, Kratz et al. 1940). They illustrate thereby the tragic affinity of romantic urbanism to totalitarian thinking which has soured their appreciation in modern architectural history writing.

Lejeune's work contributes hereby to shed light on a subject so often ignored by contemporary architectural history writing. The main contribution of the book is nevertheless to link modern vernacular architecture in Spain to the romantic modernism of 20th century Europe.

The book is well illustrated with over 400 photos and drawings. It contains a catalogue of villages planned or executed in the period between 1943 and 1970 with localisation and major morphological information. The publisher has to be commended (again) for making the subject accessible in such an opulent way.

References

Schulte-Frohlinde, J., et al. (1940). *Der Osten*. München., G. D. W. Callwey.

